

BILATERAL RELATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN WITH THE COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan's policy of open and mutually beneficial cooperation is supported in the countries of Central Asia. Neighboring countries highly appreciate Uzbekistan's efforts aimed at creating an environment of trust and close neighborliness, and Central Asian countries express their readiness to turn the region into a stable, safe, prosperous place in cooperation. This will help the rapid development of the economies of the countries of the region.*

Keywords: *Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, security in Central Asia, foreign political activity, national interest, principle, modern international relations.*

ДВУСТОРОННИЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН СО СТРАНАМИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

Аннотация. *Политика Узбекистана на открытое и взаимовыгодное сотрудничество поддерживается в странах Центральной Азии. Соседние страны высоко оценивают усилия Узбекистана, направленные на создание атмосферы доверия и тесного соседства, а страны Центральной Азии выражают готовность превратить регион в стабильное, безопасное, процветающее место в сотрудничестве. Это поможет быстрому развитию экономик стран региона.*

Ключевые слова: *Министерство иностранных дел Республики Узбекистан, безопасность в Центральной Азии, внешнеполитическая деятельность, национальный интерес, принцип, современные международные отношения.*

In today's complex environment, where global and regional changes are taking place in the world, maintaining the position of regional countries and ensuring future development can be solved on the basis of a single regional integration. As an equal subject of international relations, Uzbekistan has established an active foreign policy at the regional and global level and is developing mutually beneficial relations with foreign partners. Such consistent, clear and constructive foreign policy is recognized by international experts and observers. It is known that one of the main tasks of Uzbekistan's foreign policy is to create an atmosphere of peace, stability and security around its territory. From this point of view, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev defined the development and strengthening of friendly, close-neighborly and mutually beneficial relations with our neighbors - the countries of Central Asia - as the main priority foreign policy direction.

In the draft of the decree "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", the tasks of bringing the close cooperation in the security, trade-economic, water, energy, transport and cultural-humanitarian spheres to a higher level in terms of quality in Central Asia defined.

Among the common factors specific to the countries of the region, which encourage Central Asia to be considered as a priority direction in the foreign policy of Uzbekistan, the following can be distinguished:

- the geographical location of the countries of the region and, in particular, the fact that Uzbekistan is located in the center of the region and borders with all of them;

- similarity and closeness of national, cultural, religious and socio-economic values;
- availability of general transport and energy communications;
- rational distribution of water resources in the region;
- generality of environmental, security and stability issues in the region.

At the initiative of the President of Uzbekistan, high-level visits were made to all countries of the region. During these visits, decisions were made on global issues of mutual interest to the countries of Central Asia: in the fields of security, economy, investment, culture and ecology. As a result, in a historically short period of time, great changes took place that led to a positive turn in the relations between Uzbekistan and the countries of the region. That is, today I can tell with confidence that we have good relations with all the countries of Central Asia.

Our country relies on the basic principles of strengthening regional and international cooperation, fulfilling international obligations in good faith, respecting and protecting human rights and other universally recognized principles and norms of international law, and developing all-round good neighborly relations with neighboring countries in all aspects, cooperates with all partners on the way. The main priority of our foreign policy is the Central Asian region. Uzbekistan's policy in Central Asia is aimed at ensuring peace and stability in the region and solving important problems of regional security. Uzbekistan will make every effort to strengthen regional trade and economic cooperation, develop the transport and transit infrastructure of the region, rational and comprehensive use of water and energy resources of the Transboundary Rivers of Central Asia, ensure the ecological stability of the region, and complete the process of border delimitation and demarcation.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the policy of open and mutually beneficial cooperation carried out by Uzbekistan is supported by the countries of Central Asia. Neighboring countries highly appreciate Uzbekistan's efforts aimed at creating an environment of trust and close neighborliness, and Central Asian countries express their readiness to turn the region into a stable, safe, prosperous place in cooperation. This will help the rapid development of the economies of the countries of the region. Today's foreign policy of Uzbekistan, in particular, good neighborliness and pragmatic regional policy, not only increases the country's international prestige, but also serves to make Central Asia a stable and cooperation space with great opportunities.

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